
Assessing the Effect of Exchange Rate Fluctuation on Macroeconomic Variables in Nigeria.

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Abstract

This study evaluates how exchange rate fluctuation impacts inflation rate and foreign direct investments in Nigeria, a country that depends heavily on oil exports and faces external economic shocks. The study analyses the relationship between exchange rate, inflation and foreign direct investments by applying data analysis tools to secondary data collected between 2000 and 2019 from World Bank Database. The findings reveal weak positive relationship between exchange rate and inflation with a correlation coefficient of 0.241 at $P=0.268$ and a strong negative relationship with a correlation coefficient of -0.805 between exchange rate and foreign direct investment at $P<0.001$. The study presents perspectives on Nigeria's economic dynamics while stressing the importance of exchange rate management to control inflation and explaining how foreign direct investment (FDI) withdrawal from Nigeria is connected to the instability of exchange rate which has created an uncertain business environment for foreign investors.

Key words: Exchange rate, Inflation Rate, Foreign Direct Investment

1.0 Introduction

Macro-economic variables are indicators used in checking the general health of an economy. They are used by policy makers and economists as instruments for analysis and decision making and have been seen to have an impact on the economic growth of economies including the Nigerian economy. These macro-economic variables include Gross Domestic product, exchange rate, interest rates, inflation rates, unemployment rates, foreign direct investment, etc. Amassoma and Nwosa (2011) mentioned that it is essential to understand the interactions between the variables to overcome various obstacles evident in Nigeria with its dynamic economic environment. In this study, the focus will be on two key variables that are affected by exchange rate fluctuations: Inflation rate and foreign direct investments.

Nigeria's exchange rate system has been passing through transformation especially over the past two decades. Some periods witnessed stability while other periods witnessed volatility. Between 2000-2006, the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) made use of the Dutch Auction System (DAS) in managing the Naira and there was relative stability in the exchange rates especially with the high oil prices (Obadan, 2006). However, in 2008, the global financial crisis affected oil prices, exposing the Naira to external shocks that led to an increase in the gap between the official and unofficial rates which further increased, when oil prices dropped (Jonathan, 2011). These fluctuations led to increase in cost of imports, inflation rates, reduction in confidence of investors and general uncertainties in government policies in the country. This made exchange rate fluctuations an area of concern for economists and policy makers and the CBN adopted different policy reforms in 2017 in a bid improve the situation. According to Ha et al. (2019), when the inflation rate is on a persistent increase, and there is decline in the value of the country's currency it further contributes to the rising pressures in inflation. This leads to so much uncertainty for businesses as the country depends heavily in imported goods.

Another factor that has an impact on the economic development in Nigeria is foreign direct investment (FDI). FDI increases the availability of capital, skill development and technology to the nation and the fluctuations in exchange rates could affect investors from continually bringing new investments to the country due to this economic instability. According to Abbott et al. (2012), investors will typically seek for nations with economic stability when looking for where to invest.

The Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) implements measures to regulate exchange rate fluctuations; however, results have been inconsistent. Akpan and Atan (2015) stated that the measures applied only stabilises the exchange rate for a short-term. It is necessary to understand fluctuations in exchange rate and develop frameworks that will enable it to be effectively stabilised. Hassan et al. (2016) emphasized the importance of understanding how exchange rate fluctuations influence inflation and establish frameworks to manage them. Understanding the factors that affect exchange rate is important because the stability of the Nigerian currency is critical to having an investor-friendly economic environment. This study is carried out to analyse these relationships to offer an update on this issue which is a persistent financial issue in the country and add to knowledge regarding the effectiveness of monetary policies in Nigeria.

1.2 Statement of the problem

The fluctuations in exchange rate area dominant theme in international finance due to its impact on various economies especially developing countries. These countries have tried various strategies to stabilise the fluctuations which has led to changes in relative prices in the economy. Stability of exchange rate is a major factor contributing to price stability and economic growth having a direct impact on FDI (Ajao & Igbekoyi, 2015). In Nigeria, the

fluctuations in exchange rate have significantly influenced the economic landscape of the country. Global fluctuations in oil prices have affected the currency due to Nigeria's reliance on oil exportation and this has led to economic instability and depreciation of the currency (Ogundipe & Ogundipe, 2013). Research studies have shown that businesses often transfer costs to customers when there is volatility in the exchange rate leading to negative impact on prices and this causes inflationary pressures (Maredza & Olamide, 2017). (Adeniran et al., 2014), mentioned that the increase in exchange rate leads to an increase in the prices of imported good, pushing prices of goods and services upward and this causes inflation in the country, showing a positive relationship between fluctuations in exchange rate and inflation in Nigeria.

Fluctuations in exchange rates creates uncertainties which often makes it difficult for countries to establish pricing strategies and investment plans, making them mitigate risks by moving their businesses to more stable economies (Osinubi & Amaghionyeodiwe, 2009a). This uncertainty often makes it difficult for countries to establish pricing strategies and investment plans, making them mitigate risks by moving their businesses to more stable economies (Osinubi & Amaghionyeodiwe, 2009a, 2009b). Udoh and Egwaikhide (2008), mentioned that foreign investors have been pushed from Nigeria due to currency movements that are very volatile, creating a business environment which is unfavourable to international investors. This situation has also affected multi-national companies who experienced an increase in operational expenses impacting their profitability. According to them, this makes the value of the Naira unpredictable, reducing potential investors who naturally will seek a stable economic environment to invest, thereby making Nigeria an unattractive location for foreign investors. There are so many policy measures being implemented by the CBN to address this issue; however, the Naira keeps depreciating further (Nyoni & Nathaniel, 2018).

Asamoah et al. (2016), in their study, mentioned that though uncertainties in exchange rate may make international investors hesitant to in continuing their businesses the negative effect may change based on institutional policies developed by the country. Research carried out on the effect of fluctuations in exchange rate on inflation and foreign direct investments show a mixed result where some studies find a positive relationship between the variables and others find a negative relationship. Osinubi and Amaghionyeodiwe (2009b) carried out an investigation on the effect of exchange rate on FDI in Nigeria between 1970 and 2004 and the results suggests that exchange rate volatility had a positive and significant relationship with FDI, stating that when the naira depreciate the real inward FDI increases. Dixit & Pindyck (1994) stated that exchange rate volatility has a negative impact on FDI. Explaining that the exchange rate volatility affects the profits and makes the stream of profits are riskier. Foad (2005) supports this, stating that countries with more stable exchange rates will attract more FDIs to their locations. The level of exchange rate could influence FDI positively, because when the local currency depreciates, foreign investors are able to acquire assets at cheaper prices making the local country attractive to them (Froot & Stein, 1991). Campa (1993), however argues that firms decide to invest in a country based on expectations of future profits. Campa's model explains that the higher the exchange rate, the higher the expectation of higher profits, therefore when the exchange rate increase, FDI will also increase.

The relationship between these variables is complex and with these dynamic issues it is necessary to carry out a study to investigate the effect of exchange rate fluctuations on inflation and foreign direct investment in Nigeria, to highlight the direction and magnitude of these relationships and provide policy makers with insights that may enable them to develop the right strategies for the overall stability, economic development and sustainable growth of the Nigerian economy.

1.3 Research questions

1. To what extent does exchange rate fluctuation relate with inflation rate in Nigeria?
2. To what extent does exchange rate fluctuation relate with foreign direct investments in Nigeria?

1.4 Research hypothesis

HO1: There is no significant relationship between exchange rates fluctuation and inflation rates in Nigeria.

HO2: There is no significant relationship between exchange rates fluctuation and foreign direct investment in Nigeria.

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Theoretical Framework

2.1.1 Interest Rate Parity (IRP) Theory:

This theory was formulated by Keynes in 1930. It is also known as the theory of one price and states that the difference in interest rate between two countries should be equal to the projected changes in exchange rate between their currencies. It is further explained by the theory that if a country has a higher interest rate than another country the currency of that country in future, is likely to depreciate due to higher returns in investment. The theory shows the link between foreign exchange rates, spot exchange rates, interest rates and inflation expectations (Ho & Ariff, 2014).

2.1.2 Dunning's Theory of International Production

This theory was developed by John Dunning in 1976. It is otherwise known as the Eclectic Paradigm and it explains that companies often participate in FDI when they identify firm specific advantages, location advantages and internalisation advantages. These three factors enable the firm to have competitive advantage making them successful in the country they have identified to invest in (Sharmiladevi, 2017).

2.1.3 The Mundell-Fleming Model

This model was developed by Robert Mundell and Marcus Fleming in 1960, and it explains the IS-LM curve and shows the relationship between exchange rates, interest rate, outputs and capital flows. It helps in giving an understanding to the impact of exchange rate fluctuations on FDI especially for economies with different exchange rate regimes (Mendoza Bellido, 2017).

2.1.4 Purchasing Power Parity (PPP) Theory:

This theory was developed by Professor Gustav Cassel, in the 20th century. The theory states that in the long run, interest rates between countries will balance out to match up with price levels thereby making purchasing power uniform across international borders, with adjustments in exchange rates. The theory states that a country's currency should be depreciated to restore equilibrium when inflation rate is higher compared to another country (Chinn, 2019)

2.2 Exchange Rate and Inflation Rate

Dornbusch (1976), Stated that understanding the relationship between exchange rate and inflation is important especially in developing countries where the fluctuations will affect the price level significantly. The study carried out by Agenor and Montiel (1996), supported the above by stating that fluctuations in exchange rate affects inflation and has certain mechanisms through which it transmits. Firstly, due to openness of the economy it will affect the price of goods imported, secondly, it could increase the price of final goods and services due to import of raw materials, thirdly it could affect the price of domestic goods and services

due to uncertainties created by fluctuations in foreign currencies price and this could either boost or lower the ability of firms planning long term investments.

The Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) has consistently developed strategies aimed at stabilising the Naira however these efforts have not effectively maintained stable inflation rates. Economic stability has been made difficult due to high rate of inflation, decreasing the purchasing power of consumers (Anidiobu et al., 2018). Current inflation rates in Nigeria are likened to the early 1970's when there was an increase in revenue generated from oil, leading to the increase in government spending. It also resulted in increase in aggregate demand and no corresponding growth in domestic production output.

Orbunde et al. (2019), reported that the depreciation of the Naira and the general exchange rate fluctuations, has made financial planning and decisions on investments difficult. The instability of the Nigeria's exchange rate may be due to oil price variations, political instability and indirectly by monetary policies of other countries. Onoh and Ndu-Okereke (2018) has connected the dependence on oil as a factor affecting exchange rates and stressed the need for there to be diversification of income streams in the country. According to Henry (2019), an increase in these import costs which is driven by exchange rate volatility has impacted negatively on the economy causing inflationary pressures. This reduction in the purchasing power affects the ability of consumers to buy essential goods and services and these fluctuations also contribute to social and economic inequalities in the country(Henry, 2019).

Umeora (2010), carried out a study to examine the effect of money supply and exchange rate on inflation in Nigeria for a period of 28years between 1982 and 2009, using Multiple Regression Analysis and the results showed that money supply had a positive effect on inflation while exchange rate had a negative effect on inflation.

Danmola (2013) in the research carried out on the impact of exchange rate volatility on Macroeconomic variables, discovered that exchange rate volatility affected Gross Domestic Product, Trade Openness and Foreign Direct Investment positively, while it had a negative effect on inflation. The Ordinary Least Square was used for the study.

Imimole and Enoma (2011), investigated the impact of the impact of exchange rate depreciation on inflation in Nigeria between 1986 and 2008. The Auto Regressive Distributed Lag co-integration tool was used for this study, and it was revealed that the main causes of inflation in Nigeria were money supply, real GDP and exchange rate depreciation.

Inyiama and Ekwe (2014), carried out a study to find out the nature of association and the impact of exchange rate fluctuations on inflationary pressure and some macroeconomic variables in Nigeria from 1979 to 2010, using the Ordinary Least Squares method and the results indicated exchange rate had a positive and insignificant effect on Inflation rate

2.3 Exchange Rate and Foreign Direct Investment

Developing countries in Africa often have discussions regarding the structural changes that will be most suitable for their countries including macroeconomic policies such as expansion of non-oil exports and reducing imports to bring about economic growth (Akpan & Atan, 2012).

Another area of focus is the contribution of FDI to economic growth and development in their countries and how exchange rate fluctuations affect FDI. According to Latief and Lefen (2018), it is important to investigate the relationship between exchange rate fluctuations and FDI since the fluctuations could create risks which may discourage investors.

Ellahi (2011) carried out a study on the impact of exchange rate volatility on FDI inflow in Pakistan, using Autoregressive distribution lag (ARDL) model, time series analysis. This was carried out from 1980 to 2010 and it was discovered that while the relationship was negative in the short run, it showed a positive relationship in the long run.

Durairaj and Nirmala (2012), studied a sample in India between 1996 and 2010. The investigation was conducted on the relationship between exchange rate volatility and FDI in India. The results, using Autoregressive Distributed Lag showed an inverse relationship between the variables. They suggested a flexible exchange system for attracting FDI to India.

Sharifi-Renani and Mirfatah (2012), discovered that trade openness, GDP and Exchange rate have a positive relationship with FDI in Iran while exchange rate volatility and price of oil have a negative relationship with FDI. The Johansen Cointegration technique was used for the study.

Al-Abri and Baghestani (2015), investigated eight Asian countries between the period of 1980 to 2011 and discovered that high supply of foreign liability decreases the volatility of exchange rate in India, China, South Korea and Singapore while the results were opposite for Indonesia, Philippines and Thailand.

Mbanasor and Obioma (2017), examined the impact of exchange rate fluctuations and foreign private investments in Nigeria using ex-post facto research design. The results showed a negative and insignificant relationship between the variables. It is explained from the study that FDI in Nigeria is not determined by exchange rate but other factors such as entrepreneurial skills and technological resources.

Kim (2017), stated in the study, which covered the period of 2000 to 2015 on investigations on exchange rate volatility and its effect on Seaborne Import volume in Korea that using ARDL, the results showed a significant negative effect while the results from the Vector Error Correction Model analysis showed short-term unidirectional causality between the variables.

Kilicarslan (2018), mentioned that the stability of exchange rates help build investor confidence because they can predict the return on investment without many changes. They are therefore more inclined to channel resources towards foreign investments when there is certainty and stability. Ufoeze et al. (2018), supported this statement by stating that when exchange rates are unstable, it implies that there is uncertainty in the economy and investors will not like a situation where they cannot predict what their investment returns will be. When the exchange rate is unpredictable, it makes it difficult, deterring investment activities, and this ends up slowing down economic growth and the reverse is the case when they are predictable, by increasing employment and expanding the economy (Guzman et al., 2018).

3.0 Methodology

This study made use of ex post facto research design which enables us to measure the relationship between the variables using time-series secondary data. The data was sourced from World Bank Database Indicators, using annual data and it covered a period of 20 years, from 2000 to 2019. In measuring the relationship between the variables, the Spearman's Rank Correlation Coefficient was used.

4.0 Discussion of findings

Table 1: Relationship between Exchange Rate, Inflation Rate and FDI

		EXC_RATE	INF_RATE	FDI	
Spearman's rho	EXC_RATE	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.241	-.805**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.268	<.001
		N	23	23	23
	INF_RATE	Correlation Coefficient	.241	1.000	-.251
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.268	.	.236
		N	23	24	24
	FDI	Correlation Coefficient	-.805**	-.251	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	.236	.
		N	23	24	24

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

4.1 Exchange rate fluctuation and inflation rate

The results show a weak positive relationship with a correlation coefficient of 0.241. When exchange rate increases, there is an associated increase in inflation, however the relationship between the two variables is not statistically strong at $P=0.268$

4.2 Exchange rate fluctuation and Foreign direct investments

The results show a strong negative relationship with a correlation coefficient of -0.805. When exchange rate increases, Foreign Direct Investment decreases. It confirms a statistically significant relationship at $P<0.001$. This therefore means that with fluctuations in exchange rate, foreign investors will be discouraged, and this may be due to the uncertainty and risks that comes with these fluctuations. We therefore reject the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between exchange rates fluctuation and foreign direct investment in Nigeria.

Looking at the table, it can be observed that there is a negative relationship between inflation and FDI, though this relationship is weak with correlation coefficient -0.251, suggesting lower levels of FDI being associated with high inflation rate. The relationship between exchange rate and inflation and inflation and FDI is weak and therefore definite conclusions cannot be drawn, indicating that there may be other factors that are also influencing inflation rates and FDI in Nigeria.

5.0 Conclusion

This study has shown a clear link between dynamics of exchange rates and its effect on macro-economic variables particularly on inflation and foreign direct investments. There was moderate rate of inflation between 2000 and 2007, and this showed an increase in FDIs especially in some sectors such as the oil and gas sector. After the 2008 global crisis there was a notable volatility in exchange rates. This was also seen in 2014 when there was a collapse in oil prices. This period showed a decline in FDI and very high inflation rates. The data points to the fact that inconsistencies in domestic policies and external shocks often lead to instability in currency, reduces the purchasing power of consumers due to increase in cost

of imports and undermines the confidence of investors. While the CBN made several efforts in developing policies such as the Import Export foreign exchange window and the Dutch Auction system which brought about temporary reliefs, the fluctuations were still evident due to the Country's over dependence on oil and high dependence on import. Ultimately, the misalignments of exchange rates had a multiplier effect which had an impact on macro-economic stability thereby discouraging long term investment.

6.0 Recommendation

1. The CBN should adopt a flexible exchange rate policy that is transparent. This should be supported by interventions that are not excessive, because excessive interventions could affect the market signals and this will increase the uncertainty of foreign investors.
2. The Nigerian government should diversify its export by promoting other sectors such as manufacturing and agriculture. This will reduce the country's reliance on oil exports and further boost its foreign exchange reserves, thereby stabilising exchange rates.
3. There should be the development of other reforms such as regulatory transparency, development of infrastructure and efficiency of the judicial system. This will attract investment in other sectors, not focusing only on the oil sector and generally improve the investment climate of the country.
4. There should be an efficient coordination of both fiscal and monetary policies by the relevant authorities to bring about consistency.

References

- Abbott, A., Cushman, D. O., & De Vita, G. (2012). Exchange rate regimes and foreign direct investment flows to developing countries. *Review of international economics*, 20(1), 95-107.
- Adeniran, J., Yusuf, S., & Adeyemi, O. A. (2014). The impact of exchange rate fluctuation on the Nigerian economic growth: An empirical investigation. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 4(8), 224-233.
- Agenor, P. R., & Montiel, P. J. (1996). *Development Macroeconomics (Third Edition)*. Princeton University Press.
- Ajao, G. M., & Igbekoyi, E. O. (2015). The determinants of real exchange rate volatility in Nigeria. *Academic Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies*, 2(1), 459.
- Akpan, E. O., & Atan, J. A. (2012). Effect of Exchange Rate Movement on Economic Growth In Nigeria. *CBN Journal of Applied Statistics*, 2(2).
- Akpan, E. O., & Atan, J. A. (2015). Effects of exchange rate movements on economic growth in Nigeria. *CBN Journal of Applied Statistics*, 2(2), 1 – 14. . *CBN Journal of Applied Statistics*, 2(2), 1 – 14. , 2(2), 1-14.
- Al-Abri, A., & Baghestani, H. (2015). Foreign investment and real exchange rate volatility in emerging Asian countries. *Journal of Asian Economics*, 37, 34-47.
- Amassoma, D., & Nwosa, P. (2011). An appraisal of monetary policy and Its effect on macro economic stabilization in Nigeria. *Journal of Emerging Trends in Economics and Management Sciences*, 2(3), 232-237.
- Anidiobu, G., Okolie, P. I., & Oleka, D. (2018). Analysis of inflation and its effect on economic growth in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Finance*, 9(1), 28-36.
- Asamoah, M. E., Adjasi, C. K., & Alhassan, A. L. (2016). Macroeconomic uncertainty, foreign direct investment and institutional quality: Evidence from Sub-Saharan Africa. *Economic systems*, 40(4), 612-621.
- Campa, J. M. (1993). Entry by foreign firms in the United States under exchange rate uncertainty. *The review of Economics and Statistics*, 614-622.
- Chinn, M. D. (2019). Purchasing power parity and real exchange rates. In *Oxford Research Encyclopedia of Economics and Finance*.
- Danmola, R. A. (2013). The impact of exchange rate volatility on the macro economic variables in Nigeria. *European scientific journal*, 9(7).
- Dixit, A. K., & Pindyck, R. S. (1994). *Investment under uncertainty*. Princeton university press.
- Dornbusch, R. (1976). Expectations and Exchange Rate Dynamics. *The Journal of Political Economy*, 84(6), 1161-1176.
- Durairaj, K., & Nirmala, V. (2012). Do Exchange Rate and its Volatility Deter Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) to India? *The Indian Economic Journal*, 60(1), 130-144.
- Ellahi, N. (2011). Exchange rate volatility and foreign direct investment (FDI) behavior in Pakistan: A time series analysis with auto regressive distributed lag (ARDL) application. *African Journal of Business Management*, 5(29), 11656.
- Foad, H. S. (2005). Exchange rate volatility and export-oriented FDI. Available at SSRN 706524.
- Froot, K. A., & Stein, J. C. (1991). Exchange rates and foreign direct investment: an imperfect capital markets approach. *The quarterly journal of economics*, 106(4), 1191-1217.
- Guzman, M., Ocampo, J. A., & Stiglitz, J. E. (2018). Real exchange rate policies for economic development. *World development*, 110, 51-62.

- Ha, J., Kose, M. A., & Ohnsorge, F. (2019). *Inflation in emerging and developing economies: Evolution, drivers, and policies*. World Bank Publications.
- Hassan, B. D., Fausat, A. F., & Baba, Y. A. (2016). Impact of monetary policy in Nigeria on inflation, exchange rate and economic growth. *International Journal of Economics and Business Management*, 2(5), 67-82.
- Henry, J. T. (2019). Impact of oil price volatility on exchange rate in Nigeria. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science (IJRISS)*, 3(2), 1-16.
- Ho, C. S., & Ariff, M. (2014). Parity and non-parity determinants of exchange rates in Latin American economies. *Taylor's Business Review (TBR)*, 4, 1-20.
- Imimole, B., & Enoma, A. (2011). Exchange rate depreciation and inflation in Nigeria (1986–2008). *Business and Economics Journal*, 28(1), 1-11.
- Inyiama, O. I., & Ekwe, M. C. (2014). Exchange rate and inflationary rate: Do they interact? evidence from nigeria. *International journal of economics and finance*, 6(3), 80-87.
- Jonathan, D. D. (2011). *Contemporary Macroeconomic Developments in Nigeria: Implications for Rapid Growth and Sustainable Development*. The Centre for Economic Sustainability and Inclusive Development (CESID).
- Kilicarslan, Z. (2018). Determinants of exchange rate volatility: empirical evidence for Turkey. *Journal of Economics Finance and Accounting*, 5(2), 204-213.
- Kim, C. B. (2017). Does exchange rate volatility affect Korea's seaborne import volume? *The Asian Journal of Shipping and Logistics*, 33(1), 43-50.
- Latief, R., & Lefen, L. (2018). The effect of exchange rate volatility on international trade and foreign direct investment (FDI) in developing countries along “one belt and one road”. *International Journal of Financial Studies*, 6(4), 86.
- Maredza, A., & Olamide, E. G. (2017). THE DETERMINANTS OF MONETARY POLICY DYNAMICS IN SUB-SAHARAN AFRICA: AN EMPIRICAL INVESTIGATION. *International Journal of Arts & Sciences*, 10(1).
- Mbanasor, C. O., & Obioma, J. (2017). Exchange rate fluctuations and foreign private investments in Nigeria. *International Journal of Economics and Business Management*, 3(8), 1-17.
- Mendoza Bellido, W. (2017). Teaching Modern Macroeconomics in the Mundell-Fleming Language: The IS-MPR-UIP-AD-AS Model.
- Nyoni, T., & Nathaniel, S. P. (2018). Modeling rates of inflation in Nigeria: an application of ARMA, ARIMA and GARCH models.
- Obadan, M. I. (2006). Overview of exchange rate management in Nigeria. *Bullion*, 30(3), 1.
- Ogundipe, A., & Ogundipe, O. (2013). Oil price and exchange rate volatility in Nigeria.
- Onoh, J. O., & Ndu-Okereke, O. E. (2018). Dependence on oil income earnings and diversification of the economy—The Nigerian response. *J Dev Country Stud*, 8(2), 95-106.
- Orbunde, B., Ayogu, S., & Salifu, G. (2019). Effect of Currency Exchange, Inflation and Government Policies on Financial Reporting of Multi-National Companies in Nigeria. *Nigerian Academy of Management Journal*, 14(2), 91-103.
- Osinubi, T. S., & Amaghionyeodiwe, L. A. (2009a). Foreign direct investment and exchange rate volatility in Nigeria. *International journal of applied econometrics and quantitative studies*, 6(2), 83-116.
- Osinubi, T. S., & Amaghionyeodiwe, L. A. (2009b). Foreign Direct Investment and Exchange Rate Volatility in Nigeria. *International journal of applied econometrics and quantitative studies*, 6(2).
- Sharifi-Renani, H., & Mirfatah, M. (2012). The impact of exchange rate volatility on foreign direct investment in Iran. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 1, 365-373.

- Sharmiladevi, J. (2017). Understanding Dunning's OLI paradigm. *Indian Journal of Commerce and Management Studies*, 8(3), 47-52.
- Udoh, E., & Egwaikhide, F. O. (2008). Exchange rate volatility, inflation uncertainty and foreign direct investment in Nigeria. *Botswana Journal of Economics*, 5(7), 14-31.
- Ufoeze, L. O., Okuma, C. N., Nwakoby, C., & Alajekwu, U. B. (2018). Effect of foreign exchange rate fluctuations on Nigerian economy. *Annals of Spiru Haret University. Economic Series*, 18(1), 105-122.
- Umeora, C. E. (2010). Effects of money supply and exchange rates on inflation in Nigeria. *Journal of Management and Corporate Governance*, 2.